

Enterprise Customer Support Conversational Agent with Automated Query Resolution and Context Retention

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ABSTRACT

In modern enterprises, 'customer support' plays an important role in maintaining customer satisfaction, efficiency and enhancement of business operations. However, an increasing number of customer requests make this manual support much expensive, time-consuming, and often inconsistent. To overcome the existing limitations, an AI-driven Enterprise Customer Support Conversational Agent (EC-CSCA) capable of delivering an automated Enterprise Customer Support Conversational Agent was proposed, which provides an accurate, and context-aware responses. The proposed EC-CSCA adopts Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) with transformer-based language models to extract knowledge from the previous enterprise documents and generates a humanised response. From the industries, firms and organizational resources such as Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ), manuals, and the company policy documents are converted into vector embeddings using Sentence Transformers, and stored in a Facebook AI Similarity Search (FAISS)-based semantic database. A Conversation Memory Manager (CMM) stores previous user conversation, enabling multi-turn dialogue and continuity of conversation. The proposed system improves response accuracy, reduces dependency on human agents, a enables 24×7 automated support, and the solution is scalable and applicable to domains such as e-commerce, banking, telecommunications, IT services, and enterprise help-desk environments, etc.,

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world customer support agents are a basic and act as a key component of enterprise service operations, handling user queries of organization, complaints and service requests. Traditional customer support processes are dependent on manual effort or human agent,

which cause high cost, slower response time, and inconsistent service outcomes. Now by increasing digitalization and customer interaction boost these challenges.

The conventional chatbots are implemented in many enterprises. These chatbots are ‘rule-based’ and depend on predefined responses or intent-matching frame works, which has several drawbacks which lead to lack of adaptability, failing to handle some unseen queries, and not remembering previous conversations of messages. As a result, the customers may experience incorrect responses. As technology continues to advance in NLP and LLMs creating more opportunities features for conversational systems through AI. Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) is an AI module which helps LLM and NLP for getting perfect, accurate and updated responses by extracting the information of data from external data source, which makes verified response, through document and contextually relevant. However, RAG shows scalable storage, and dialogue-level memory integration.

In the present article an AI-based enterprise conversational agent that integrates RAG, FAISS-based vector search, Sentence transformer embeddings and dialogue manager which provide automation, scalable, and context-aware customer support.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

An important improvement in conversational systems, is the integration of conversation memory and multi-turn dialogue management where an agent in an enterprise system, shows and maintains the previous context with a dynamic role adaptation, recognition accuracy, clear and logical responses, and user satisfaction. Similarly, from the previous studies on Context-aware conversational systems for business applications was proposed and reported that maintaining context from past conversation context reduces the laying-off, maintains the flow across conversations, and improves overall task completion rates [1,3,6,7]. Over the past decade, customer support automation (CSA) has evolved significantly, transitioning from simple rule-based chat systems to intelligent conversational agents capable of contextual understanding and knowledge-grounded response generation. This review highlighted the evolution of AI-based conversational agents from rule-based architectures to transformer-driven systems, emphasizing their growth and adoption across enterprise domains such as customer service, banking, and e-commerce, with a development of transformer-based language models [2]. Early designed ‘enterprise chatbots’ primarily depend on predefined scripts and keyword-matching techniques, which has a limitation of ability to respond beyond structured and predefined query patterns, but the systems performed well

enough for simple and repetitive tasks but failed when faced with unclear information or unseen user inputs, which reveals a major disadvantage of repeating the login process and the conversations. A machine-learning (ML) based dialogue system was introduced, with an intent identification and entity recognition to enable more flexible user interactions and remained restricted by static training datasets, but with limited domain adaptability, and frequent manual retraining requirements, which reduces the scalability in enterprise development [4,5]. Later, a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) architecture was introduced, where it combines neural retrieval mechanisms with generative models by retrieving relevant information from enterprise knowledge sources and an embedded information generates a response generation process. The retrieved content is transformed into vector embeddings and stored in semantic databases to support quick access. Techniques such as Sentence Transformers and FAISS-based indexing allow fast similarity matching search and responses informed by previous context. Significantly improving accuracy, transparency, and response consistency in enterprise customer support systems. Furthermore, based on real results evaluations of chatbot performance in customer service environments confirm that context-aware and knowledge-grounded conversational agents achieve better results than traditional systems in terms of response relevance, efficiency, and user satisfaction. All this shows the importance of integrating contextual memory, semantic retrieval, and transformer-based generation in enterprise conversational agents [8,9].

Hybrid dense retrieval systems combine sparse keyword-based retrieval with dense embedding-based retrieval methods were used, which improves search accuracy by capturing both lexical, and semantic similarities between queries and documents. But the drawback faced is the enhancement of computational complexity and huge storage requirements [10].

Enterprise knowledge retrieval systems have been developed to assist employees and depends on structured databases and predefined knowledge schemas such as documents and emails. By reorganizing the enterprise data into structured formats, the system can provide a clear and accurate responses to employee queries [11].

In the proposed work, an AI-based enterprise conversational agent was suggested which works on various technologies and generates the suggestions as answers to the customer queries.

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed web application maintains an architecture with major components shown in Figure 1. The web application initiates with ‘user interface’, which contains user guides, manuals,

and policy files are dumped and converted into structured text segments. Large documents are breakdown into small chunks, meaningful sections to find correct information with accuracy by admin. At user side sends query. Secondly, a ‘query processing’ module was developed to perform operations such as text normalization and cleaning, where it ensures that user inputs are structured which are suitable for downstream processing. This module enhances the effectiveness of embedding and retrieval operations.

Later, an Embedding Model was initiated as one of the modules to transform a textual data into dense vector form, where both ‘user queries’ and ‘document chunks’ are encoded into a semantic space, which delivers an effective similarity match based on the meaning of the contextual. A FAISS Vector Database and Indexing module was developed to store the data and get indexed by FAISS, and checks the nearest-index similarity search over large-scale datasets. The Retrieval Module identifies the most relevant document chunks using similarity search and compares the current query embeddings with related stored vectors to extract top-k(k=4). These retrieved contexts are forwarded to the generation module for answer synthesis. The Response Generator uses a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) approach which acts as a local large language model and generates responses grounded in retrieved knowledge. This ensures factual consistency and minimizes hallucination in generated outputs. Finally, the Response Delivery module acts and the generated response is returned to the user via the interface in real time, and presented in a structured and conversational manner for better understanding of the user. The total implementation of the present proposed work is shown in Figure 2.

Figure-1: System Architecture

Figure-2: Implementation Framework

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The proposed system analysed multiple enterprise style, real-time customer query scenarios, including frequently asked questions (FAQs), policy-related inquiries extracted from organizational documents, and context-dependent multi-turn interactions. The chatbot effectively retrieved relevant knowledge fragments using a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) framework and generated accurate, context-aware responses. The integration of FAISS-based semantic search enabled rapid similarity matching between user queries and document embeddings, resulting in significantly faster response times compared to manual support and traditional keyword-based search methods. Overall, the system produced more consistent responses, reduced the workload of human support staff, and improved efficiency in handling common customer queries, demonstrating its suitability as a scalable and intelligent enterprise customer support solution.

The results reveals that the RAG with enterprise knowledge bases, not like the traditional rule-based chatbots. This proposed system is used to handle different queries, remembers the context of conversational data and provide accurate response based on the organizational documents as verified document source. The quality of response depends on the quality and completeness of reference enterprise documents. Incomplete and outdated knowledge sources may affect the response quality and accuracy and reduce efficiency. So, the regular updating of documents and feedback improves the reliability.

Further, the proposed can be modified with extra features, and can be extended its services with multiple languages, learning from the user's feedback, through analysing the feedback.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The proposed solution demonstrates the accuracy, quality, improving efficiency, service reliability, and customer experience in enterprise support agents.

This study presented an enterprise-oriented customer support conversational agent that combines automated query handling with contextual continuity through the integration of Retrieval-Augmented Generation, semantic embeddings, FAISS-based vector retrieval, and conversation memory management. By replacing traditional manual and rule-based support approaches, the proposed system enables scalable access to verified enterprise knowledge and supports coherent multi-turn interactions. These outcomes highlight the effectiveness of the proposed approach for enterprise-level customer support systems, operational performance, and service dependability. And

clear decrease in human action. These outcomes highlight the effectiveness of the proposed approach for enterprise-level customer support systems.

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